

Curriculum Management in Indonesia at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah North Sumatra

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the planning of the curriculum at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra. Then describe the organization of curriculum resources at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra. Furthermore, to describe the implementation of the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah curriculum program in North Sumatra. Then to describe the supervision of the Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah Tsanawiyah curriculum in North Sumatra. Lastly, to describe the curriculum evaluation of the Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah Tsanawiyah in North Sumatra. This research is qualitative in nature. The process of extracting data in a holistic manner either by means of in-depth interviews with a series of questions, observation in the form of observations, and collecting documents with the aim of obtaining correct and valid data. There are 5 (five) findings which are the results of this study.

Keywords: Curriculum, Management, Madrasah Tsanawiyah, Al-Ittihadiyah.

INTRODUCTION

The curriculum used by Islamic education institutions is more directed at the needs of the community and tends to prioritize religious lessons. Spiritual lessons are the main lessons to be learned. Increasingly, the curriculum in Madrasahs has begun to be open to receiving general lessons combined with spiritual experiences (Zailani & Aziz, 2020: 648). Curriculum development is actually an effort to improve the quality of education in Indonesia. It is an instrument that helps educational practitioners to meet the needs of students and the needs of society. Curriculum development is a tool to help teachers carry out their teaching duties and meet community needs. Curriculum development never stops, it is an ongoing and continuous process in line with the development and demands of the times and changes that occur in society. To succeed this program, a policy that fully supports the program is needed. The policy steps taken by madrasah are efforts to maximize and efficiency in achieving the stated educational goals (Mesiono et.al.2019: 61).

Islamic organizations empower people through maximizing education. This is because this field is the primary need of the people. In addition, there is such a strong urge from the teachings of Islam to study knowledge, so that it is categorized as an individual obligation. The rise of ignorance and the low quality of education are the main reasons why education is the main goal of Islamic organizations (Anzizhan & Syafaruddin, 2015: 39). Al-Ittihadiyah is an Islamic organization that continues to concentrate on contributing to efforts to advance Muslim education through educational institutions that have been developed from basic to tertiary education. The presence of Al-Ittihadiyah has historically been motivated by the desire to organize an Islamic education system that is more orderly, more modern, and organized into an organization, especially Islamic schools or colleges that have not been incorporated in a particular organization (Al-Rasyidin, 2018: 52-53).

The existence of Islamic education institutions that are managed by religious organizations, such as Al-Ittihadiyah in Indonesia, is truly well established and gives great hope to be able to play an active and positive role in the formation of the nation's personality. In the process, Al-Ittihadiyah educational institutions must be able to create human resources who have moral, ethical and spiritual strength in building their nation, especially in entering the era of globalization or the 21st century (Anzizhan & Syafaruddin, 2015: 143). This has also been done by other religious organizations such as Muhammadiyah, Nahdhatul Ulama and especially Al-Washliyah and Al-Ittihadiyah who were born and developed in North Sumatra and have a big role in building education that is needed by the community through educational institutions that are managed nationally, especially in North Sumatra, either in the form of a school or madrasah.

Al-Ittihadiyah has quite a number of educational institutions ranging from elementary to tertiary levels. The role of Al-Ittihadiyah as the manager of educational institutions cannot be denied, because Al-Ittihadiyah plays a role in various lines and regions to

educate and advance the nation. The educational institutions managed by Al-Ittihadiyah are managed in such a way as to maximize their contribution to building a better education. One of these efforts is carried out with good management of curriculum management. Al-Ittihadiyah as an Islamic organization that was born and raised in North Sumatra from the start has attempted to formulate and compile an Islamic education curriculum that can be used in all Islamic education institutions it supports. As for lesson plans, they have been formulated since the beginning as in 1957. The subjects are: Qiraah, Worship, Tawheed, History / Date, Tajweed, Chat, Imlak, Latin writing, Reading Latin, Counting and Indonesian Language (Soiman, 2018: 85-87).

The current implementation of the Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah madrasa curriculum is in accordance with that set by the government. At present, the Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah madrasas are unable to maintain the style of their curriculum according to their inception due to the curriculum policy that has been set by the government (Kamenag curriculum). The Tsanawiyah madrasas are MTs Al-Ittihadiyah Mamiyai Bromo, MTs Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang, MTs Al-Ittihadiyah Pangkalan Masyhur, and MTs Al-Ittihadiyah Percut Deli Serdang.

METHOD

This research is focused on the curriculum management of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra, therefore the use of a qualitative research approach is suitable to be used in revealing facts as empirical truths in this study. The Tsanawiyah who were the subjects of this qualitative research were MTs Al-Ittihadiyah Mamiyai Bromo, MTs Al-Ittihadiyah Laut Dendang, MTs Al-Ittihadiyah Pangkalan Masyhur Medan, and MTs Al-Ittihadiyah Percut Deli Serdang. The qualitative research approach as a scientific method is often used and implemented by a group of researchers in the social sciences, including education and management education. A number of reasons are also put forward, the point is that qualitative research enriches quantitative research results. Qualitative research is carried out to build knowledge through understanding and discovery. According to Sugiono (2014: 1) this qualitative research approach is often called the naturalistic research method, because the research is carried out in natural conditions (natural setting).

RESULT AND DISCUSS

Curriculum Management

Management is a special process when examined where management consists of planning, organizing, implementing and controlling actions, each of which is used by both science and expertise and which are followed sequentially in order to achieve the targets that have been set from the start. Curriculum management is the whole process of joint efforts to facilitate the achievement of teaching goals with an emphasis on effort, improving the quality of interaction and teaching. Meanwhile, understanding the curriculum itself can be understood in a narrow and broad sense (Arikunto & Yuliana, 2008: 95). Curriculum management is a curriculum management system that is cooperative, comprehensive, systemic, and systematic in the context of realizing the achievement of curriculum goals (Rusman, 2009: 3).

Curriculum management is a process or curriculum management system in a cooperative, comprehensive, systemic, and systematic manner to refer to the achievement of the curriculum objectives that have been formulated. In the curriculum management process, it is inseparable from formal social cooperation between two or more people with the help of supporting resources. The implementation is carried out with certain work methods that are effective and efficient in terms of energy and costs, and refer to predetermined curriculum goals (Hamalik, 2006: 16). Curriculum management is a curriculum as a design for educational education which has a strategic position in all aspects of educational activities. Curriculum management is the process of utilizing all elements of management in order to maximize the achievement of the goals of the educational curriculum implemented in educational institutions (Syafaruddin & Amiruddin, 2017: 39). This study focuses on curriculum management in Indonesia at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah North Sumatra.

Planning the Curriculum of Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah in North Sumatra

The existence of a curriculum is very strategic in increasing the effectiveness of learning developed by educational institutions. Principals, deputy principals, teachers and education personnel have a role to support the maximization of the achievement of learning goals, which are marked by changes in student behavior, both in cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. That way, students really achieve the learning outcomes expected and planned by the teacher through the learning process both inside and outside the classroom (Syafaruddin & Amiruddin, 2017: 23).

The curriculum is an educational program that contains various teaching materials and learning experiences that are programmed, planned and systemically designed on the basis of applicable norms which are used as guidelines in the learning process for educational staff and students to achieve educational goals. Curriculum management is the whole process of joint efforts to facilitate the achievement of teaching goals with an emphasis on effort, improving the quality of interaction and teaching. Meanwhile, understanding the curriculum itself can be understood in a narrow and broad sense.

Planning (planning) is the selection or setting of organizational goals and determination of strategies, policies, projects, programs, procedures, methods, systems, budgets and standards needed to achieve goals (Rusman, 2009: 58). Planning is the process of

preparing, determining, and utilizing resources in an integrated and rational manner so that the activities to be carried out can run effectively and efficiently in accordance with the expected goals (Arifin, 2014: 25). Curriculum planning is part of the initial activities to formulate curriculum concepts that become educational programs in schools, not only learning plans, but plans for curriculum concepts that will be taught in schools. That means that curriculum planning covers a very broad spectrum, both plans regarding objectives, subject matter / content, methods, media, and evaluation are set to serve as guidelines in implementing curriculum in the form of learning (Syafaruddin & Amiruddin, 2017: 56).

Based on the findings of research related to the planning of the curriculum at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra, information was obtained that curriculum planning was carried out before entering or at the beginning of the new school year. Those involved in curriculum planning are the head of madrasah, supervisors, committees, WKM I in the field of curriculum, teachers and foundations. The curriculum refers to the curriculum from the Ministry of Religion which is socialized to all teachers. Based on the theory, what is applied by Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra is correct. Curriculum planning is part of the initial activities to compile curriculum concepts that become educational programs in schools, not only learning plans, but plans for curriculum concepts that will be taught in schools. This means that curriculum planning covers a very broad spectrum, both plans regarding objectives, subject matter / content, methods, media, and evaluation are set to become guidelines in implementing the curriculum in the form of learning. This has been implemented by Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra.

Organizing Curriculum Resources at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra

Curriculum management is the process of utilizing curriculum resources which includes planning, organizing, implementing and monitoring to achieve learning and educational goals. George R. Terry who was quoted from S. Nasution's book stated that; Organizing is the act of striving for effective behavioral relationships between people, so that they can work together efficiently, and obtain personal satisfaction in carrying out certain tasks, under certain environmental conditions in order to achieve certain goals or objectives (Nasution, 2006: 72).

Curriculum organization is a very important principle for the curriculum development process and is closely related to the objectives of delivering learning materials, determining the content of learning materials, determining how to deliver learning materials, determining the form of experience to be presented to educators and determining the role of educators and educators in curriculum implementation.

Based on the findings regarding the organization of curriculum resources at the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah in North Sumatra, it was found that the most important roles in organizing curriculum resources were the Head of Madrasah and WKM I in the curriculum sector. Organizing curriculum resources is from the Head of Madrasah to WKM I, then WKM I gathers teachers and holds meetings with teachers in the field of study (Subject Teacher Deliberation) in accordance with directions from the Ministry of Religion and the Foundation.

Based on the theory and findings, the organization of curriculum resources at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra is correct. What is implemented by Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra in organizing is to seek effective behavioral relationships between the teams at the madrasah, so that they can work together efficiently, and gain personal satisfaction in carrying out their tasks in carrying out curriculum programs, in the condition of the madrasah environment which has a mandate burden from the community to achieve the mandated educational goals or objectives.

Implementation of the Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah Curriculum Program in North Sumatra

In the framework of implementing the curriculum in each education and learning unit, it must be in accordance with the plan, so readiness is needed, especially readiness for implementation. Whatever curriculum and learning design or planning you have, the success of the implementation of learning is very dependent on the implementer as well as the duties of the principal, teacher, or supervisor. Even though the curriculum is still simple, if the teacher has the ability, enthusiasm and high dedication, the result will be further than a great curriculum design, but the ability, enthusiasm and dedication of the teacher is low. This means that professional teachers are a prerequisite for the effectiveness of implementing the curriculum at a superior learning level (Syafaruddin & Amiruddin, 2017: 75).

Based on the findings, information was obtained that the steps for implementing the curriculum program at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah were socializing the madrasah curriculum to teachers in the form of meetings. Then after that all the teachers make a learning program design (RPP). Then, the lesson plans were checked by WKM I in the field of curriculum and then approved and signed by the head of the madrasah. After that it is implemented in teaching and learning activities (KBM). The next stage is supervision of the head of madrasah regarding the suitability of the teaching and learning process with the predetermined curriculum. After that, at the end of the school year, an evaluation of the curriculum achievement is conducted.

Based on the theory and field findings, the steps for implementing the curriculum program at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra are correct. The stages are carried out in accordance with the proper procedure. The implementation of the curriculum is based on the potential, development and condition of students to master competencies that are useful for themselves. This is because the Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah in North Sumatra has various conditions and in general it is helping the government in providing decent education that is easily accessible to all people in an effort to educate the people. In

this case, students must get quality educational services, and have the opportunity to express themselves freely, dynamically and pleasantly in accordance with the objectives of Islamic education.

Supervision of the Curriculum of Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah in North Sumatra

The supervisor of the learning process is carried out through monitoring, supervision, evaluation, reporting, and regular and continuous follow-up activities. Supervision becomes very strategic especially since everyone in the organization must realize the importance of supervision so that irregularities do not occur. However, it needs to be underlined that Islamic values teach fundamentally the highest control over human actions and efforts, both individually and organizationally, is Allah Almighty (Mesiono, 2019: 106).

Based on the information obtained with the findings related to the supervision of the curriculum at the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra, information was obtained that the supervision of the curriculum at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah was supervised by madrasah supervisors from the Ministry of Religion, besides that it was also supervised by the Foundation and the head of madrasah. In addition, the madrasah committee also participates in monitoring the learning process so that the curriculum can run well.

Based on the theory and findings related to the supervision of the Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah curriculum in North Sumatra, madrasahs are helped by the efforts and cooperation of various parties in the supervision of the curriculum implemented by Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra. The evaluation stages, both in the form of: monitoring, supervision have been carried out at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra, with the help of the Madrasah Head, Madrasah Supervisor, Foundation and the madrasah committee.

Evaluation of the Curriculum of Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah in North Sumatra

Evaluation is the provision of information for the benefit of facilitating decision making in various steps of curriculum development. Information relating to the program as a whole or only relating to several components. Evaluation also applies the selection criteria, data set and analysis (Rusman, 2009: 98). Curriculum evaluation is perfecting the curriculum by revealing the curriculum implementation process that has succeeded in achieving the stated goals. Curriculum evaluation is intended to examine the overall curriculum performance in terms of various criteria, the performance indicators evaluated are effectiveness, efficiency, relevance and program feasibility (Wahyudin, 2014: 148).

Curriculum evaluation is an important process to determine the results achieved. Here it can be emphasized that the existence of evaluation can be a process for reviewing educational progress and making innovations and new ideas to develop the next curriculum. The position of the curriculum evaluation results cannot be ignored until the next evaluation is carried out. It is understood that there must be follow-up by evaluators and curriculum designers even to the teacher as a form of responsibility for managing schools as a form of public accountability. In other words, the evaluation results are feedback that can be used to improve school performance. The main function of evaluation activities, namely diagnosis, prediction, selection and ranking or rating of tasks or activities that have been carried out by educational practitioners (Syafaruddin & Amiruddin, 2017: 108).

Based on information findings related to the evaluation of the curriculum at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra, curriculum evaluation in madrasahs is carried out after it has been made, examined, implemented and supervised by the Head of Madrasah, Madrasah Committee, Foundation and Supervisors after that evaluation. What needs to be considered in curriculum evaluation is the conformity of the curriculum with the learning process plan made by the teacher, as well as the suitability of the lesson plan with the implementation of the teaching and learning process. Those involved in the curriculum evaluation process are the Head of Madrasah, WKM I in the field of curriculum and teachers.

Based on the theory and findings related to the evaluation of the Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah Madrasah in North Sumatra, it has been done well. In the curriculum evaluation process, the Principal of Madrasah, WKM I in the field of curriculum and teachers was directly involved. Curriculum evaluation is a systematic effort to collect information about a curriculum to be used as a consideration of the value and meaning of the curriculum in a particular context. The results of curriculum evaluation can also be used by teachers, principals as education implementers in understanding and fostering student development, selecting learning materials, selecting learning methods and tools, assessment methods and other educational facilities. Sukmadinata also argued.

CONCLUSION

Based on the descriptions and findings contained in this study regarding the Management of the Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah Madrasah in North Sumatra, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Planning for the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah in North Sumatra is carried out before entering or at the beginning of the new school year. Those involved in curriculum planning are the head of madrasah, supervisors, committees, WKM I in the field of curriculum, teachers and foundations. The curriculum refers to the curriculum from the Ministry of Religion which is socialized to all teachers.
2. The organization of the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah curriculum resources in North Sumatra is from the Madrasah Head to WKM I, then WKM I gathers teachers and holds meetings with teachers in the field of study (Subject

- Teacher Deliberation) in accordance with directions from the Ministry of Religion and the Foundation. As for the most instrumental in organizing curriculum resources is the Head of Madrasah and WKM I in the field of curriculum.
3. Implementation of the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah curriculum program in North Sumatra, namely by disseminating the madrasah curriculum to teachers in the form of meetings. Then after that all the teachers make a learning program design (RPP). Then, the lesson plans were checked by WKM I in the field of curriculum and then approved and signed by the head of the madrasah. After that it is implemented in teaching and learning activities (KBM). The next stage is supervision of the head of madrasah regarding the suitability of the teaching and learning process with the predetermined curriculum. After that, at the end of the school year, an evaluation of the curriculum achievement is carried out.
 4. Supervision of the curriculum of the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah Madrasah in North Sumatra is supervised by a madrasah supervisor from the Ministry of Religion, in addition to that, it is also supervised by the Foundation and the head of madrasah. In addition, the madrasah committee also participates in monitoring the learning process so that the curriculum can run well.
 5. Evaluation of the curriculum at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Al-Ittihadiyah in North Sumatra is carried out after it has been made, examined, implemented and supervised by the Head of Madrasah, Madrasah Committee, Foundation and Supervisors, after which an evaluation is carried out. What needs to be considered in curriculum evaluation is the conformity of the curriculum with the learning process plan made by the teacher, as well as the suitability of the lesson plan with the implementation of the teaching and learning process. Those involved in the curriculum evaluation process are the Head of Madrasah, WKM I in the field of curriculum and teachers.

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